

AN EVALUATION OF THE IDENTITY AND WORKINGS OF EKWENSU IN IGBO PHILOSOPHICAL THOUGHT

**Dr. Patricia Ebere Nwazonobi, Innocent Aliama, Mbe Kenneth Okorochoa,
Jonah Ophoke Ogboloko and Somadila Divine Ugwumma**

*Department of Philosophy, Religion and Peace Studies, Faculty of Social Sciences and Humanities,
Ebonyi State University, Abakaliki, Nigeria.*

Email: *patricianwazonobi@gmail.com, aliamajunior@gmail.com, mbeokorochoa@gmail.com,
ogbolokojonahchukwuemeka@gmail.com, divinesomadilau@gmail.com*

Phone: *08037750765, 080644814846, 08037590831, 07034551042,
08168087852*

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Abstract: *Igbo people are highly religious. They have a polytheistic faith because they believe in numerous gods. None of the gods in Igbo traditional society acts independently of or in opposition to the Supreme Being (Chukwu). Each one has a unique purpose for the good of humanity, though. In Igboland, Ekwensu is one of these many gods. The search for the identity and workings of Ekwensu in Igbo philosophical thought has generated a great deal of discussion among academics. Ekwensu, the god of violence and battle in Igbo philosophy, is said to possess unique tricks that help Igbo business owners strike advantageous deals to increase their earnings. Unfortunately, the early missionaries who arrived in Igboland, among other things, vilified the glorious Ekwensu deity. They also persuaded Igbo Christians to believe that Ekwensu is the equivalent of the Christian Devil, who opposes God and will be sent to hellfire on the last day. It is against this backdrop that this study is carried out to examine the real identity of Ekwensu in Igbo philosophical thought. Both primary and secondary data gathering were used. The investigation discovered, among other things, that Ekwensu is not an equivalent of the Christian Devil; rather, he is a warlord who has helped the Igbo people in times of war and commerce before the early missionaries arrived and corrupted it. The study comes to the conclusion that early missionaries used the demonization of Ekwensu as a tool to cajole Igbo Christians to accept their faith. Based on the findings, the study suggests that since Ekwensu has been found to have socioeconomic*

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ramifications in Igbo traditional society, it should not be relegated to the background.

INTRODUCTION

The Igbo people have a strong religious belief. Chukwu is the sole Supreme Being recognized by them. According to Ukaegbu (2005), the Igbo belief in Chukwu Okike Abiama is reflected in their common names, such as Chukwudalu, Chukwuebuka, Chukwubuikem, Chukwuka, Chukwuemeka, and others. In Igbo cosmology, Ebuka (2003) posits that Chukwu Okike Abiam is so revered that people only contact him through intermediaries. These intermediaries, according to Kalu (2018), are referred to as divinities, gods, or goddesses and are thought to have been created by God. In the hierarchy of spirits, which also includes Ala, Amadioha, Anyanwu, Ekwensu, Ikenga, and others, God is the primary source of everything.

In Igbo culture, these minor spirits are common and specifically function as components of Chineke, or Supreme Being (Onebunne, 2011). Because the Igbo people only believe in one Supreme Being and numerous gods, their religion is polytheistic in nature. In Igbo traditional society, no god or goddess operates independently of or in opposition to the Supreme Being (Chukwu Okike Abiama). Each serves a unique purpose in promoting socio-religious harmony (Okpalike and Chukwu 2022). The coming of the missionaries to Igboland adversely affected the Igbo traditional belief system. They described every aspect of

Igbo religion as fetish. And any aspect of the culture that they found difficult to understand, they tagged "barbaric." The damage the early missionaries caused to Igbo culture was best described by Achebe (1958, p. 141) when he said that:

The Whiteman is very clever. He came quietly and peaceably with his religion. We were amused at his foolishness and allowed him to stay. Now he has won our brothers, and our clan no longer acts like one. He has put knife on the things that held us together and we have fallen apart.

As Okpalike and Chukwu (2022) point out, it was clear that the white missionaries needed a medium to convey the main principles and components of Christianity in order to fit it to the Igbo worldview, philosophy, and culture. The Igbo language is the only one that can fulfill this need. They looked for synonyms for these concepts and elements in the Igbo lexicon; those they were unable to locate were left in the missionaries' foreign tongue. Okpalike and Chukwu (2022) assert that education was crucial and that introducing literature in African languages was crucial to achieving the declared missionary purpose. Thus, in order to spread the Christian message, they started writing and translating concepts and ideas in African languages. Hence, they created categories that were extremely alien to Igbo culture in order to

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make Africans view their indigenous religion as inferior. These categories include, but are not limited to, the ideas of heaven and hell. Corroborating the view, Ebo (2019) posits that the Igbo had never heard of heaven or hell before the coming of the missionaries. They consider any place outside of the community, whether it is among the living or in the ancestors' company, to be isolated. Because of this, the missionaries did not convert many elderly people. To them, the concept of a heaven separated from the community and the company of their ancestors was just as wicked as the hellfire, which the missionaries advised them to stay away from at all costs.

The gods in Igboland were even affected by the survival of Christianity. Okpalike and Chukwu (2022) note that missionaries have described the worship of numerous Igbo deities as wicked and idolatrous. The identity and character of Ekwensu were perverted and demonized; a deity who was discovered to be the patron spirit of ancient Igbo warriors and a heroic Igbo deity of war was misinterpreted as the ontological and conceptual counterpart of the Christian Devil. In order to vilify the ancient Igbo religion, early Christian missionaries devised evangelistic techniques that included the purposeful annihilation of the identity and character of the Ekwensu deity in Igboland (Opata, 2005; Nwosu, 2018). In other words, the cult of Ekwensu has declined throughout Igboland due

to the ongoing damage caused by European Christian missionaries and colonialists to the Igbo trado-religious environment. According to Okpalike and Chukwu (2022), the name of this ancient Igbo deity now evokes great fear and connotes evil, especially to the average Igbo living in this era. The description of the identity and character of Ekwensu as the ontological and conceptual equivalent of the Christian Devil, according to Okpalike and Chukwu (2022), seems to be a relatively new idea, separate from the traditional Igbo people's religious beliefs, and a direct result of the arrival of early Christian missionaries in Igboland.

It is consequent upon the missionary denigration of the identity of Ekwensu in Igboland that this study is carried out to investigate the real identity of Ekwensu and its workings. To achieve that, the study adopted both primary and secondary methods of data collection. Expository theory is the theoretical framework adopted for the study to expose and bring to bear the real identity of Ekwensu. Therefore, the study found that Ekwensu in Igbo cosmology is not actually the rebellious devil who would ultimately be thrown into the burning furnace known as "hell" together with his companions for challenging Chineke, the God of Creation, which was invented by Christians. Hence, there is no hell in the Igbo belief system, where bad people will suffer, and no heaven, where good people will be rewarded,

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and there is no god, goddess, or deity that acts independently of or in opposition to the Supreme Being in Igbo traditional belief.

Objectives of the Study

The research aims at achieving the followings specific objectives. They are to:

1. Expose the identity of Ekwensu in Igbo philosophical thought
2. Examine the socio- economic identity and workings of Ekwensu in Igboland
3. Investigate the extent early missionaries bastardized the identity of Ekwensu

Research Questions

This research provides answers to the following questions

1. What is the real identity of Ekwensu in Igbo philosophical thought?
2. What are socio- economic identities and workings of Ekwensu in Igboland?
3. To what extent did the early missionaries bastardize the identity of Ekwensu?

Review of Related Literature

Phenomenology of Ekwensu in Igbo Philosophical Thought

The Igbo etymology of Ekwensu was studied by Anizoba (2008). E kwe n su = E kwe m su = E kwe O su = E kwe ya E-su. "E" is the Igbo impersonal subject marker, according to Anizoba; hence, E delü = "One wrote." E meligo fa=they have been defeated by an unidentified subject. "Kwe" is an Igbo verb that means "to agree." For example, "Kwe na ï ga-eme ya"

means "Agree that you will do it." "Su" is a verb that means "to start abruptly" or "to start a fight," as in Agha e-su = War breaks out. According to Anizoba, the meaning of the term "Ekwensu" is thus: If one agrees (E kwe), then something happens (ya e-su). Akandu (2023) claims that the term "Ekwensu" is composed of the words "ikwe" and "osu," where "ikwe" means "to allow" and "osu" means "fulfilled" or "fulfillment." Ekwensu does not act without your consent. In other words, you must give him permission before he does anything.

In traditional African thinking, evil is entirely related to humans and not Ekwensu. The position is supported by Okpalike and Chukwu (2022), who point out that it is clear that Ekwensu and the Devil are not the same thing. As a result, the Christian Devil is completely alien to Igbo religious and ontological thinking, and Igbo morality does not allow for the fundamental deprivation of good. In the Igbo traditional moral code, humans are inherently good-oriented, capable of evil, and only able to suffer the consequences of their deeds. Tempels (1945) makes the case in Bantu Philosophy that the concept of good or evil is founded on human thinking and not on a power above man; rather, it is wholly dependent on man. According to the Igbo and Yoruba cosmologies, evil is still centered on man and is the result of human behavior. One may argue that the majority of natural disasters, such as earthquakes, floods,

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and droughts, are caused by human activity. In traditional African belief, evil individuals are those who harbor malice, use evil words, or commit wrongs. This is true even when it is asserted that evil is caused by invisible forces; evil is always connected to a perpetrator. The identity and character of Ekwensu in the Igbotrado-religious worldview, according to Agboanike (2019), do not support the presence of an absolute good God and an absolute bad spirit, the devil, engaged in a never-ending struggle for dominion over humanity and the cosmos. What the original identity of the Ekwensu deity is as conceived within the framework of the ancient Igbotrado-religious worldview, then, if the Christian missionaries were successful in demonizing the identity and character of the Ekwensu as the ontological or conceptual equivalent of the Christian Devil?

Umeh (1999) states in response to the aforementioned question that Ekwensu is the most attractive deity in both ancient Egypt and Igboland. It is the Eagle spirit of war and victory, gliding along the earth with innumerable victories. It is a war deity with innumerable victories, known as Oha Obala/Ora Obala. In Igbo Afa, it is revered as Ugo Tagbulu Agwo, the eagle who pecked the evil snake to death. It has also been established that Ekwensu is one of the benign lunar deities. Ora Obala, also known as Oha Obala in Igbo Afa, literally translates to "child of the sun" or "child of the

God of light," which includes the moon, the eagle, and Ekwensu. To call Ekwensu a devil or an evil spirit is truly ludicrous and absurd on the part of any Igbo person, since the eagle, the moon, and the child of light have never been connected to evil or evil ones, but rather to success, achievement, and the beautiful ones.

Ekwenu is one of the many deities in Igboland whose socio-religious identity was undeniable before the arrival of the early missionaries. According to Okpalike and Chukwu (2022), Ekwensu is an intrinsic element of the Igbo Cosmo-religious world and does not oppose any deity, including Chukwu, Ezechitoke, or Obinigwe, like all other deities/gods in Igbo Traditional Religion. Since the Igbo were unaware of hellfire prior to the Christian era, Ekwensu had nowhere to operate. Okpalike and Chukwu (2022) further note that if God let deities/godsplay a crucial role in running the universe, as many scholars believe, then Ekwensu is simply one of them, along with Ogwugwu, Ofufe, Aro, Ngene, Aro bi n'agu, Udo, Agwu, and others. These gods, spirits, and energies, such as Ekwensu, were created to improve human life. Their main goal is to ensure that people in the areas where they are born and reside have the greatest possible lives. While some Igbo identify Ekwensu as a violent god and the source of evil, Metuh (1991) asserts that Ekwensu is an Arusi and not the devil. Although its function varies among Igbo groups,

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most Igbo view Ekwensu as a spirit of violence because it incites violence, which can be very helpful during war, and that is why warriors and headhunters invoke him. Nwobodo (2021), in partnership with Metuh, contends that the spirit known as Ekwensu is not the same as the Christian Devil. The reason is that in many regions of Igboland, such as Asaba and Ukpok, which are authentically Igbo communities, deities are worshipped like Ekwensu. However, because of linguistic issues, the Christian Devil has been widely known and referred to as Ekwensu.

Methodology

Both primary and secondary data collection methods were used for the study. The researcher used the primary technique of data collection to obtain information from people who lived in areas where some Ekwensu cults, their shrines, and people/places committed to them are still practiced today. Equally, the researchers used a substantial amount of primary material, which might be appropriately categorized as either participant observation or ethnographic methodology. Comparatively, both published and unpublished works from the body of existing literature that are related to the current research were used.

The Identity of Ekwensu in Igbo Philosophical Thought

There is ample evidence that Ekwensu was a heroic deity in Igboland, despite the western

demonization of its cult and identity. For Opata (2005), several Igbo villages have shrines devoted to the cult of Ekwensu. The Onu-Ekwensu shrines at Umundu community in Udenu Local Government Area; Iheaka in Igbo-Eze South; the Iwhu Ekwensu at Nkalagu, Nimbo, Uvuru, Abi, Ugbene, and Anuka, all in Uzo-Uwani Local Government Area, Enugu State; and the Ekwensu annual trade-religious festival known as Uta-Ekwensu are a few noteworthy examples (Opata, 2005). A communal shrine that is exclusively devoted to the worship of the Ekwensu deity has been established in Anaku, a well-known hamlet in Ayamelum Local Government Area, Anambra State (Opata, 2005). The cultic activities and the location of this shrine clearly illuminate the identity and character of Ekwensu as conceived in ancient Igbo religion (Okpalike and Chukwu, 2022). Ekwensu Anaku, a deity in the Ayamelum Local Government Area in Anambra State, according to Nnabugwu (2021), is still respected and honored by the community as their major community deity and a protector of their community against invaders.

The cults of Ekwensu had tremendous impacts on the Igbo people in every town and location where they lived prior to the arrival of missionaries in Igboland. According to Opata (2005), the Onu-Ekwensu shrine in the Umundu community was typically the site of the last ritual ceremony before someone was given

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the traditional title of Ozioko in some Igbo Nsukka communities. He also notes that the Ekwensu shrine in Iheaka served as a place of prayer where community members would come to ask Ekwensu for prayers. People appeal for the protection, favor, and benevolence of the deity in these prayer requests. Nimbo, a community in the Uzo-Uwani Local Government Area, Enugu State, has a shrine dedicated to the worship of Ekwensu. This shrine was very active before the coming of the missionaries. The corpses of those who were assumed to be qualified to be ancestors based on the good life they lived were laid in state in this shrine amidst praises centered on their heroic deeds, integrity, honesty, diligence, and hard work, and so on (Opata, 2005).

Okpalike and Chukwu (2022) contend that there was a shrine of Ekwensu in Amalla, Udenu Local Government Area, Enugu State. The annual Akatakpa cultural festival is held in honor of the Ekwensu, and it is strictly forbidden for people of questionable character to attend or approach the shrine. From the foregoing, Jideofor (2025) argues that it is unthinkable to equate the Ekwensu deity with the Christian devil. For Jideofor (2025), Ekwensu as ontologically conceived in Igbo Nsukka is a deity who confronts and forbids evil; he is neither the source of all evil nor the antithesis of the Supreme Being. For Isichei (1969), the yearly Ine or Ika-Ekwensu trado-

religious festival in Asaba, Ugwu-Ekwensu in Ukpok, Ani-Ekwensu in Achi, Ohia Ngene Ekwensu in Ufuma, Ohia Ekwensu in Uga, and so forth are all excellent examples of ancient Igbo trado-religious festivals established to honor, celebrate, and honor Ekwensu for his role in defending the people's lives against their adversaries. There is the existence of natural objects like mountains, lands, forests, and so on, dedicated in honor of Ekwensu. Considering that there are natural features like mountains, farms, forests, and so on that are devoted to Ekwensu. Isichei (1966) notes the obvious fact that these places are not regarded as evil by the various communities where they exist, which seems to be a clear testament that the ancient Igbo never conceived Ekwensu as an evil deity whose identity and character are congruent with the Christian devil.

In many Igbo regions, it is well known that Ekwensu had shrines and was revered before Christianity arrived. Above all, it is suggested that many Igbo groups consider Ekwensu to be their founding father or ancestor (Ifesinachi, 2025). In modern times, some Igbo clans have changed their names since they are cajoled to believe that Ekwensu is associated with the Christian Devil. Supporting the view, Ndubisi (2019) emphasizes that "Obi Chukwu replaced Obi Ekwensu as the name of the Isiala Ngwa community in Isiala Ngwa North Local Government, Abia State." Whereas, some

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related groups continue to use their original names, in addition to those that have changed. In support of this, Opata (2005) contends that people also have names that honor Ekwensu, citing Nru N'ato Ezike Ekwensu in Nsukka L.G.A. and Imilike Ogo Ekwensu in Udeno L.G.A. According to him, Lejja, a lineage in Enugu State, used to bear the name. In the Okposi group in Ebonyi State, a lineage shrine goes by this name, and individuals can be found bearing the name. In Isiala Ngwa (Abia State), there is a community that also used to bear the name Ezi (Delta State), the festival heralding that of the New Yam is Ekpensu—a dialectal variant of the standard Igbo Ekwensu. In Akpugo Nkanu (Enugu State), Ekwensu may be used as a praise name of someone who has made a great accomplishment. In Ekwulobia and Ukpok (both in Anambra State), there are hills named after Ekwensu. From the foregoing, Opata (2005) opines that one could infer that the word Ekwensu as it appears in these names has many implications and connotations, and it may be said that he is an ancestor of the communities.

Ekwensu was so regarded and revered before the arrival of Christianity that some people used it as a praise name in towns like Akpugo in Enugu State and Anaku in Anambra State. Ekwensu may be considered a town hero or a commendation name for someone who has accomplished tremendous achievement

(Nnabugwu, 2021). Ndubisi (2019) supports the argument that if Ekwensu is an ancestral name and the name of a warlord whose power swept across Igboland, the name would not necessarily be connected to evil, particularly given the moral and ontological way the Christian Devil is portrayed. Furthermore, traditional Igbo society loathes crime, evil, and abomination very strongly. It cannot then be imagined that many communities will, knowing that Ekwensu is evil, decide to answer to that name.

Socio-economic Identity and Workings of Ekwensu in Igboland

Ekwensu is a heroic god of war and mercantile among the Igbo people. According to Kanu (2015), the Ekwensu deity is the ancient Igbo patron spirit or warlord, and the ancient Igbo warriors rarely consult or invoke it when lives, property, sovereignty, or the territorial integrity of a community are at great risk. In agreement, Kanu (2018) and Metuh (1991) summarize the Ekwensu deity as a spiritual force or an invincible spiritual war phenomenon of ancient Igbo warriors, whose identity and character are distinct from the Christian Devil. The traditional Igbo identity of Ekwensu, as the leading indigenous war deity, is further revealed by Abba and Onunkwo (2016). It is his divine duty to assist ancient Igbo warriors in winning a war against a fierce foe. In terms of the economy, Echo (2021) demonstrates that the Ekwensu deity is renowned for his skill at

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deception, cunning, and negotiating, marketing, and industries. In commerce and other discussions, he is also recognized for his unparalleled cunning and craftiness. When crucial wisdom is required or during challenging discussions, people turn to him in prayer (Nnabugwu, 2021).

The protection of the Igbo people from unwarranted attacks by their combatants is one of the many functions of the Ekwensu deity, as Nwoja (2024) notes. According to the ancient Igbo trado-religious worldview, Ekwensu is a high-ranking Igbo war deity, spiritual force, or ultra-metaphysical defensive energy that the indigenous ancient Igbo used to resist and defeat a vicious enemy. Achake (2023) and Echo (2021) assert that the invincibility and indomitability of the ancient Igbo warriors against their enemies, both nearby and distant, particularly the invading British army, were attributed to the Ekwensu. It is a historical fact that the last native Nigerian tribal army to be defeated by the British was the ancient Igbo warriors. It took the British army almost thirty years to defeat the ancient Igbo warriors, despite their superior firepower, war experience, and scientific and technological advancements (Akunna, 2025). The missionaries' observation that Ekwensu was the spiritual force behind the ancient Igbo warriors' invincibility in the face of British imperialism and colonialism is plausible as the reason for

this defeat. Hence, they vilified Ekwensu as evil and the Christian Devil's equivalent, which caused the ancient Igbo to give up their cult of Ekwensu (Echo 2021; Achake 2023).

Western Bastardization of the Identity of Ekwensu

Ekwensu is the most denigrated deity in Igboland; the mere mention of Ekwensu causes some annoyance to the average Igbo person. Ikenna (2024) points out that it is obvious that Igbo Christians have believed in Ekwensu as the conceptual and ontological equivalent of the Christian Devil since the early European Christian missionaries brought Christianity to Igboland. Okpalike and Chukwu (2022) support this belief, arguing that the demonization, destruction, and misrepresentation of Ekwensu's identity and character could be attributed to the actions of the early Christian missionaries in Igbo land. The idea that Ekwensu is the Igbo version of the Christian Devil is so widely held among the Igbo that even the very small percentage of indigenous Igbo people are aware that Ekwensu's original identity and character, as reflected in the ancient Igbo trado-religious worldview, contradicts Ekwensu's Igbo Christian identity and character.

Some people believe that Ekwensu cannot be considered the conceptual equivalent of the Christian Devil, whereas Igbo Christians believe that Ekwensu might be compared to the

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Christian Devil. According to Ndubisi (2019) and Metuh (1985), early missionaries indoctrinated the vast majority of Igbo people to believe that Ekwensu is the Christian Devil's equivalent. This belief is made clear in the majority of discourses on traditional Igbo religion and ethics as well as in the majority of translations of Christian songs, hymns, prayers, and chants. Even in everyday Igbo talks, Ekwensu's schemes are blamed for all kinds of temptations and wicked deeds (Ndubisi, 2019; Nwobodo, 2021). The murder of Akukalia by Ebe is attributed by Achebe (1964) in "Arrow of God" to the action of Ekwensu, the bringer of evil. As the master spirit, Ekwensu rules over all other agents of evil (Basden, 1966). Aguwa (1987) contends that "the devil, or Ekwensu, is a wicked spirit who causes great harm even when he is not provoked." He would always be Chukwu's (God's) adversary. He and his team have the power to make one do evil by controlling his emotions and will. Since Ekwensu is seen as so dangerous, unyielding, and unforgiving, there are no temples dedicated to him.

Igbo-Trado-Religious Justification of the Nature of Ekwensu

Opata (2005) and Isichei (1969) strongly agree that the Ekwensu divinity is not the Devil, Satan, or Lucifer. They anchored their position on the existence of some indigenous Igbo communities where there exist shrines, cultural

practices, and festivals confirming the existence of the Ekwensu phenomenon, its identity, and its character. For Metuh (1991), the conceptualization of Ekwensu as an ontological and conceptual equivalent of the Christian Devil is at variance with the ontology of Ekwensu in Igbo religion; he further observes that Ekwensu enjoys a special relationship with the Igbo Supreme Being Chukwu and is not an archenemy whose activities are antithetical to the divine will of the Supreme Being.

Ekwensu cannot be demonized as a result of its violent nature. Opata (2005) supports this viewpoint by pointing out that the violent or bloody nature of Ekwensu's ancient Igbo identity and character does not provide an ontological basis for demonizing the deity to the point of ontologically equating it with the Christian devil. According to Ekwunife, who was quoted by Ndubisi (2019), Ekwensu does not own a monopoly on aggressive force; rather, all deities share it when provoked. Furthermore, Ndubisi (2019) contends that the Ekwensu in a given agent turns into a positive force when this violent force is employed to right wrongs or punish a malevolent criminal or someone who took a false oath. However, Ekwensu turns into a destructive, aggressive power when it is employed arbitrarily to destroy individuals without cause, damage their property, or even harm their health. Metuh (1999) quoted Arinze saying that in Igboland, Ekwensu does not have

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a monopoly of anger and violence, noting that there are deities like "Udo," "Okpimodu," "Ununnachi," "Omaliko at Abatete," and others who take pleasure in causing pain virtually arbitrarily and at the very least in response to provocation.

Okpalike and Chukwu (2022) refuted Aguwa's (1987) portrayal of Ekwensu as a demonic spirit that lacks a shrine and is not offered sacrifices by pointing out that the Ekwensu Anaku shrine is situated in the center of the community, specifically in Isiokwe Umuezeagu village in Anaku. Other deities' shrines, on the other hand, are located deep in impenetrable forests, distant from the neighborhoods. On this, Okpalike and Chukwu (2022) contend that one obvious and remarkable aspect of the Ekwensu shrine is its proximity to people's compounds, which suggests that the people view the shrine and the deity as an important aspect of their lives rather than as something bad. Furthermore, Okpalike and Chukwu (2022) aver that the deity Ekwensu Anaku does not symbolize evil, condone evil, or engage in evil. In the Omambala sub-cultural zone, Ekwensu Anaku is revered as a deity who protects people from a variety of issues and serves as a moral check on those who engage in witchcraft, sorcery, or charms that destroy innocent lives, cause suffering and misfortune to their fellow humans, and so on, and who are afraid to approach the shrine of the deity. Opata (2005)

asserts that there is a shrine of Ekwensu called Onu Ekwensu at Iheaka, Igbo Eze South Local Government Area, Enugu State. Following the presiding priest's sacrifice,

There was a communion, during which the consumables of the sacrifice were shared and consumed. Opata (2005) quoted Anyika asserting that the deity to whom such a sacrifice is offered is viewed as a good deity rather than an evil spirit or deity. How can Ekwensu be urged to deny its own nature if it is a wicked deity? Therefore, early missionaries' demonization of Ekwensu in Igboland was an attempt to promote Christianity as the ideal substitute for Ekwensu. Ndunesokwu (2016) supported the idea by claiming that early Christian missionaries demonized Ekwensu after learning that the Igbo people's ancient religion did not account for the existence of the devil or Satan, without whom it would be difficult to place the Christian God within a Christian ideology. As a result, they impersonated the Devil to recreate Ekwensu.

Findings

1. The study found that Ekwensu was a heroic deity in Igbo land before the arrival of Christians, not a counterpart of the Christian Devil. The remnants of the Ekwensu shrines and cults in various areas of Igboland are clear evidence.
2. The study revealed that Ekwensu is the most important indigenous Igbo war deity, and

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it is its divine duty to help the ancient Igbo warriors defeat a fierce foe. It is also well-known for its cunning, skill, and status as the god of industry, marketing, and negotiating. When crucial wisdom is required or during challenging discussions, people offer prayers to it.

3. The study found that early missionaries in Igboland mostly denigrated the identity of Ekwensu. In the mind of some ordinary Igbo people, the very mention of Ekwensu is a nuisance. The idea that Ekwensu is the conceptual and ontological counterpart of the devil has undoubtedly been widely held by the Igbo people since post-colonial times.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, the study comes to the conclusion that it is inaccurate to compare Ekwensu to the Christian Devil, who opposes God and whose fate is the hellfire on the last day. This is because, according to Igbo ontology, gods, goddesses, and deities are given distinct roles and are answerable to the highest being. Therefore, no one acts against Chukwu Okike Abiama or in isolation. The Igbo people did not believe in the Christian notions of hellfire, where the Devil and his followers will suffer, and heaven, where the good will be rewarded, before the missionaries arrived. Therefore, the early missionaries in Igboland constructed scenarios such as comparing Ekwensu to the Christian Devil and teaching heaven and hell in

order to persuade and market the Christian God to the Igbo people.

Recommendations

1. Based on the findings, the study recommends that Ekwensu should not be equated with the Christian Devil; rather, be projected as a heroic deity in Igbo land prior to the coming of Christian. On the basis that the traces of the shrines and cults of Ekwensu in some parts of Igboland.

2. The study recommends that the identity of Ekwensu should not be jettisoned since it is discovered to be so instrumental, whose divine responsibility is to aid ancient Igbo warriors to achieve war victory against a vicious enemy. And equally known for its mastery of tricks, craftiness, and god of negotiation, marketing and industries.

3. Like every other deities in Igboland, Ekwensu should be positively represented. Hence, it does not mean harm to Igbo people. Demonizing the identity and workings of Ekwensu was a mere scenario created by the early missionaries to introduce the Christian God in Igboland.

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